

DIFFERENTIATION OF EXPRESSIVE AND VISUAL ARTS WITHIN THE TYPES OF ART

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ABSTRACT

At one time, Abdurauf Fitrat said: "Art means craft in the dictionary, one

At first glance, it may seem that Fitrat revives the meaning of the word "art", the essence of art. What are the meanings of the word "good"? In fact, the word "art" used in our language has a wide range of meanings. For example, the word "art" has different meanings in each of the combinations such as "art of painting", "to master the art of pottery", "made with high art". Nevertheless, they have common points that unite the facets of meaning expressed by the word "art", which is that this word is related to the concepts of "beauty", "skill", "taste" in all three cases.

No matter how widely the word "art" is used in our living language, naturally we are interested in its lexical meaning, not its literal meaning. In the term, art means the creative activity aimed at the artistic mastery (and change) of existence based on the laws of human beauty, as well as all the things created as a result of it. So, understood in this sense, everything that is created with skill and taste based on the laws of beauty is related to art. That is why we distinguish between "practical art" and "artistic (fine) art".

Fine arts include painting, music, sculpture, cinema, we belong to the theater. As long as we understand "art" in the broadest sense if we distinguish between applied and artistic types of art, their should have generalizing and different aspects. The generalization here is that both are laws of beauty is created with taste and skill. As for the different aspects, the most important of which is that the product of applied art is human if it serves to satisfy the material needs, the examples of artistic art are aimed at satisfying the spiritual and spiritual needs of a person. So, a product of applied art is intended for use in everyday life, and at the same time gives him pleasure. For example, no matter how elegant and beautiful the bowl made by the potter is, we drink tea (in general, a drink) in it. Both the elegantly crafted bowl with an eye for substance and the soul bowl are equal in terms of practical utility. However, an elegantly made cup is not only a tool for drinking tea, but also gives him pleasure and lifts his mood. However, giving pleasure is a secondary function of the bowl.

Therefore, the value of a product of applied art is primarily determined by its usefulness. Now, for comparison, let's take, for example, a statue created by an ancient Greek sculptor. When creating the statue, the Greek did not intend to use it in practice. Suppose he made a statue of one of the gods he found. The sculptor first created that goddess in his imagination, in the image he was able to imagine with the power of creative fantasy - in a frozen moment he could see the beauty, power, mercy and anger of his goddess, he enjoyed it, admired it, worshiped it, and sealed this situation in stone. While looking at the statue, the viewer gets the same pleasure and admiration, and does not think of using the statue for any other purpose. We see that the sculpture transferred the pleasure and admiration of another person to another person, his psyche. While some art forms depict, others express. Let's say that music is an art of expression, the composer expresses his experiences through melodies, and these melodies create a certain mood in our psyche. When listening to music, based on that mood, each listener imagines a unique scene and situation. That is, the composer expressed the experiences born under the influence of a certain image - he did not describe the image itself, and the listener imagines that image based on his experiences.

From the above, it can be seen that both the bowl and the statue were created with taste and skill based on the laws of beauty. That is, applied art and fine art are also products of aesthetic activity. Human activity aimed at mastering and changing existence based on the laws of beauty is called aesthetic activity.

The difference between the types of art is also seen in the uniqueness of their reception by the recipient (reader, listener, viewer). Take, for example, the difference between the process of perceiving a landscape painted by an artist and a landscape described in words in an epic work. We see the painting as a whole: that is, we see it first as a whole, then we go from the whole to the parts (looking at the details). On the other hand, when perceiving the landscape in fiction, we proceed from the part to the whole: at first we get acquainted with the order of the details, and at the end a whole landscape is formed before our eyes. If the receiver directly accepts the works belonging to certain types of art, the presence of an intermediary - the performer - is required for the acceptance of others.

Art reflects reality using an artistic image (image). The concepts of art and artistic image complement each other, enrich and explain each other. Art is fully expressed through the medium of an artistic image. Artistic image is an important "cell" of art, without which art does not work, artistic image defines the main characteristic of art. That's why it's artistic image is the main stage in revealing the nature of art.

The secret of art is closely related to the secret of the artistic image in many ways. Since ancient times, people have been trying to understand the secret of the artistic image. The concept of image is a component of the theory of cognition. "Image" means the reflection of things and events in the human mind. A person perceives the external world in the form of an image through his intuition, perception, imagination, understanding, etc. The source of the artistic image is "living life". The artistic image is a re-understanding of reality and belongs to aesthetic concepts.

In art, the sense of individuality is absorbed into the content of the artistic images created by the artist-creator. Nothing compares to an artistic image saturated with the artist's experiences. Therefore, artists describe their main characters as "I - myself". Artistic creativity

is always filled with unique experiences and emotions. In art, "personality" is a necessary condition for the creation of an artistic image.

References:

1. Jonattan Culler. Literature theory: A very short introduction. OUK 2011.
2. Ортега-и-Гассет. Дегуманизация искусства.-М.: Радуга, 1991
3. Тэн И. Философия искусства.-М.,1996
4. Потебня А. Эстетика и поэтика.-М.,1976
5. Борев Ю.Б. Эстетика –М., 1988.
6. Минералов Ю.И. Теория художественной словесности.-М.,1999
7. Бекчанова, С. (2023). СТАНОВЛЕНИЕ ЧЕЛОВЕКА ЛИЧНОСТЬЮ СКВОЗЬ ПРИЗМУ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ И КУЛЬТУРНОЙ РЕАЛЬНОСТИ. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 3(4 Part 4), 32–36. извлечено от <https://inacademy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/13213> DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7867146>.
8. Бекчанова Солиха Давлатназаровна. (2022). ШАХСНИНГ КАСБГА БЎЛГАН ҚИЗИҚИШИ, ЛАЁҚАТИ ВА ҚОБИЛИЯТЛАРИНИ АМАЛИЙ ЎРГАНИШДА ЖАҲОН ТАЖРИБАСИ. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH, 2(12), 774–780. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353435>.
9. Бекчанова Солиха Давлатназаровна. (2022). ОСНОВНЫЕ СОСТАВЛЯЮЩИЕ ПРАВСТВЕННОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ ШКОЛЬНИКА. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6483370>. The possibilities of using textbooks during mother tongue classes.
10. Shahob Sharofitdinovich Shodiev. Academia An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal "Interpretation of philosophical terms and concepts as an essential subject for linguistic researches of XIX-XX centuries, held in Russia and Europe" 590-98 10.5958/2249-7137.2020.01171.4
11. Shahobiddin Sharofiddinovich Shodiev. Bakaev Najmiddin Bakaevich. expressions.. (2020). The role of the Latin language in the history of world statehood. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 05 (85), 367-372. SoI: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1/TAS-05-85-71> Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS> Scopus ASCC: 1203. THE ROLE OF THE LATIN LANGUAGE IN THE HISTORY OF WORLD STATEHOOD
12. Sh.Sh.Shodiyev. N.B.Bakayev. M.N.Khafizova, S.N.Ostonova " SHAKESPEARS LEXICON: REASON WORD AS A DESIGN OF THE CONCEPT OF THE ABILITY OF THE HUMAN MIND TO ABSTRACTION, CONCLUSION " Theoretical and Applied Science, 162-166, 2020
13. Ш.Ш. Шодиев, Д.Я.Шигабутдинова. «ШЕКСПИРОВСКИЙ ЛЕКСИКОН: СЛОВО REASON КАК ОБОЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПОНЯТИЯ СПОСОБНОСТИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО УМА К АБСТРАКЦИИ УМОЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЮ» Инновационный потенциал развития науки в современном мире, 189-197, 2020 General cultural and educational values of ancient-classic latin language TN
14. Shodiev Shahobiddin Sharofiddinovich, & Majitova Nafisa Zokirovna. (2021). IDEAS ABOUT AN IDEAL PERSON, LANGUAGE, PROSPERITY IN THE EVOLUTION OF PUBLIC AND

POLITICAL VIEWS OF THE UZBEK JADIDS OF THE BEGINNING OF THE XX CENTURY.
Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 1(3), 5–8. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4925897>

15. Шодиев Шаҳобиддин Шарофиддинович. (2022). "МАКБЕТ" ВА "АБУЛФАЙЗХОН" ТРАГЕДИЯСИДА ФАЛСАФИЙ СЎЗЛАР ВА NATURE /ТАБИАТ" ВА SOCIETY / ЖАМИЯТ ТУШУНЧАСИ. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH, 2(12), 1142– 1150. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7390238>

16. Shahobiddin Sharofiddinovich Shodiev, Najmiddin Bakaevich Bakaev, Nafisa Zainiddinovna Tasheva STUDYING PHILOSOPHICAL REALITIES OF THE RENAISSANCE EPOCH, BASED ON THE STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF PHILOSOPHICAL TEXTS // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/studyingphilosophical-realities-of-the-renaissance-epoch-based-on-the-structural-analysis-ofphilosophical-texts>. 17. Shahob Sharofitdinovich Shodiev. *Academicia An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* "Interpretation of philosophical terms and concepts as an essential subject for linguistic researches of xix-xx centuries, held in russia and Europe" 590-98 10.5958/2249- 7137.2020.01171.4

17. Sh.Sh.Shodiyev. N.B.Bakayev. M.N.Khafizova, S.N.Ostonova " SHAKESPEARS LEXICON: REASON WORD AS A DESIGN OF THE CONCEPT OF THE ABILITY OF THE HUMAN MIND TO ABSTRACTION, CONCLUSION " *Theoretical and Applied Science*, 162-166, 2020.